

Multi-Modal Sensor for Fingertips of Anthropomorphic Grippers

Tanzeel Ahmad Fazal, Gianluca Laudante, Michele Mirto, Olga Pennacchio and Salvatore Pirozzi
Engineering Department, Università degli Studi della Campania, “Luigi Vanvitelli”, Aversa (CE), Italy

Corresponding author: tanzeelahmad.fazal@unicampania.it

Abstract—The trend of robotic manipulation in complex and unstructured environments necessitates the integration of various sensory modalities to enable accurate and adaptive grasping and control. This paper presents the design, development, and integration of a multi-modal sensor for robotic gripper, incorporating tactile sensing based on optoelectronic technology, Time of Flight (ToF) for pre-touch sensing, and Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU). Tactile sensing is fundamental for perceiving fine-grained surface textures, detecting pressure, and enabling precise object manipulation. Time-of-Flight pre-touch sensors offer proximity information with ultra-low latency, by enhancing environment interaction or anticipatory human-robot responses. IMUs provide critical motion and orientation data to track gestures and postures, as well as temperature information about grasped objects. The developed remarkably compact sensor, measuring only 12.5×20 mm, making it suitable for integration on the fingertip of any robotic gripper, and sensor system aims to enhance the gripper’s abilities by providing real-time feedback about object properties, pose estimation and dynamic interactions during grasping and manipulation tasks. The novel multi-modal sensor has very smaller size equivalent to human fingertip and more robust design that yields the higher sensitivity, higher flexibility and less noise. Extensive tests on its measurement capabilities evaluated sampling frequency, noise, and precision. The sensor has been successfully integrated into a commercial three-fingered gripper, demonstrating its practical application in robotic manipulation tasks.

Index Terms—Multi-Modal Sensor System, Optoelectronic Based Tactile Sensor, Time of Flight (ToF), Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU).

I. INTRODUCTION

In the recent years, the field of robotics has witnessed remarkable innovations, enabling robots to perform a wide range of tasks in diverse environments. One of the most challenging and critical aspects of robotics is effective manipulation of objects, which requires precise control and understanding of the interaction between the robot’s end-effector and the objects being manipulated. The success of such tasks is highly dependent on the sensory information available to the robot, enabling it to adapt its actions in response to changing conditions and uncertainties in the environment. Multi-modal sensors are innovative devices capable of acquiring and processing numerous types of sensory data simultaneously, such as tactile, proximity, and inertial measurements, improving the functionality and versatility of robotic systems. These sensors offer a comprehensive understanding of the environment and

objects, improving the robot’s interaction and manipulation competences. Integrating numerous sensing modalities into a compact unit reduces space and weight, which is crucial for size-constrained applications. The fusion of data from multiple modalities leads to more accurate and reliable measurements, reducing noise and enhancing precision. Furthermore, multi-modal sensors are cost-effective, as they eliminate the need for separate sensors for each modality, lowering overall system costs. They also simplify the integration process, streamlining development and deployment. Their versatility make it capable for use in a wide range of applications, from industrial automation to healthcare, due to their adaptability to various environments and tasks. Literature reflects many solutions based on the two approaches for sensors [1]: the first one based on continuous deformable medium between the receptors and the contact, which enables few receptors to interpolate the data among them; the second one based on array of tactile receptors or independent contacts, that easily enables the identification of contact location. Different transduction technologies, (e.g., optoelectronic [1], capacitive [2], [3], resistive [4], [5], and magnetic [6], [7]) may utilized both sensor based approaches, depending on weight, dimension, compatibility and targeted task. In past, huge number of relevant papers has been reported about tactile sensing. Suen et al. [2] introduced concept of capacitive tactile sensing of three axial force through five concentric shape independent sensing electrodes. Makihata et al. [3] designed more precious capacitive distributed sensor that uses custom designed ASIC matrix inside the silicone wafer structure. Wang et al. [4] developed a tactile sensor with 3x3 array of resistive sensing elements enclosed by conductive rubber bubbles. Liu et al. [5] and Klimaszewski et al. [8] proposed a solution based on distributed tactile sensor uses the matrix of piezoelectric or resistive sensing elements covered by flexible material for the detection of contact pressure. The papers [6] and [7] presented the tactile sensors for 3-axis contact forces estimation using Halls-Effect based sensing elements which determines the displacement of deformable silicone layer. Hence, multiple commercial solutions have also been presented, e.g., BioTac, Contactile, Gelsight. Robots can utilize additional cameras to detect objects from greater distances, whereas tactile sensing is limited to direct contact with objects. Typically, tactile sensors are placed on the robot’s end-effector, such as grippers or robotic hands,

allowing them to sense areas closer to objects that may be unreachable to cameras. By strategically integrating proximity sensors with tactile sensors, robots can engage in pre-touch sensing. This capability facilitates the estimation of an object's position and shape during the phases of robot's approach and grasping [9], [10]. Unlike vision-based and tactile sensors, pre-touch sensors operate at an intermediate range, offering advantages from both sensor categories. When mounted on the robot's end-effector, they are more resistant to occlusion compared to cameras. When placed at a closer range, they have the potential to provide more precise measurements. Hence, pre-touch sensors do not necessitate physical contact with objects similar to camera or depth sensors. Moreover, proximity sensors would empower the robots to get information for estimation of pose and shape through particular scanning approach [9]. In recent years, proximity sensor with different technologies (e.g., electric field, acoustic and optical) have been already introduced by many researchers in robotic manipulation and other smart systems. Widely used Electric Field (EF) pre-touch sensors [10] utilizes the electric field produced when AC signals are emitted between two electrodes, which irradiate objects in close proximity. By examining changes in the electric field, these sensors can restructure information about the irradiated objects. Although EF sensors exhibit commendable performance, their effectiveness is constrained to conductive materials possessing a high dielectric constant, making them less efficient when used with objects made of paper or rubber. Acoustic sensors with seashell effect have been presented in [11]. In this technology, a cavity along microphone are used to scan the target and to restructure the information of object shape by scrutinize the resonant frequency spectrum changes. Optical sensors have consistently recognized their reliability as a technology capable of operating effectively across a diverse array of materials, yielding precise and accurate outcomes. As illustrated in references [12], [13], the optical method has exhibited exceptional efficacy in obtaining highly precise measurements of object shape and distance. It is important to note that these approaches involve the measurement of reflected light from objects, necessitating careful consideration of intrinsic challenges associated with explicit calibration procedures required for variable colors and surface reflectivity. Time-of-Flight (ToF) technology appears as a promising solution among optical pre-touch sensors, addressing conventional issues related with optical sensors. Extensive research as reported in [14], [15], demonstrates the advantages of ToF sensors, such as their inherent lack of need for calibration, robustness, and accuracy across a wide spectrum of materials. Lancaster et al. [14] particularly utilized the proximity sensor information along with depth camera based point cloud to enhance the estimation of object pose and Sasaki et al. [15] employed the Time of Flight sensors during grasping tasks by enhancing the robustness of robot hand positioning. Hence, pre-touch sensor provides the object shape and pose estimation as well as contributing in real time safety applications, e.g., Human

Machine collaboration.

This research endeavors to advance the capabilities of robotic manipulation through the integration of multi-modal sensor systems. By combining tactile sensing, Time of Flight, and IMU technology, the proposed approach seeks to empower robots with the ability to perform complex manipulation tasks with improved adaptability and efficiency. To complement tactile feedback, we integrated ToF sensor and IMU into the sensor system. ToF sensor provides the information about proximity, object shape and estimates the pose as well as IMU captures the gripper's motion and orientation data, allowing for precise tracking of its movements in space. This data, when fused with tactile information, facilitates real-time adjustments and hand-eye coordination, crucial for robust manipulation. The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section II and III provides the detail design of hardware and software architecture as well as in Section IV its integration and testing, and lastly conclusion and future work.

II. SENSOR TECHNOLOGY

The working principle is based on the designing of a multilayered PCB, microcontroller based, constituted by an IMU and a discrete number of optoelectronic photo-reflectors (named "taxels" and consisting of Light Emitting Diode and Photo-transistor couples), arranged in a specified configuration enclosed by a deformable layer. The same microcontroller, through a specific connector available on the PCB, allow also the connection of the ToF sensor module, designed by authors in [9]. It completes the hardware of this multi-modal sensor. The connector is mounted by allowing the integration of ToF on the top side of multi-modal sensor. The target objectives of the whole system are the following.

- 1) To transduce the contact data into deformations measured by the optical components. The light emitted by the LEDs is reflected by the bottom side of deformable layer and it is measured by the photo-transistors. The measured signals depends from the amount of deformations, related to external contact. The measuring points, spatially distributed, correspond to the tactile map. These data can be used, for example, to evaluate the shape of grasped object or reconstruct the external forces.
- 2) To continuously monitor the close range by means of the proximity data acquired through the ToF sensor. These data can be used, for example, to avoid obstacles/collision, to interact with the environment/human or reconstruct locally the 3D information from the scene.
- 3) To continuously monitor IMU data, which can be used, for example, to estimate the pose, to prevent slippage events or to evaluate the object temperature.

The exploded CAD model of multi-modal sensor with all parts aligned is reported in the Fig. 1. Some mechanical parts (e.g., grid, PCB support) have been designed to complete the assembly and realized in ABS plastic by means of 3D printing technology. Also the deformable pad, made of silicone, has

Fig. 1. CAD of an assembled sensor (left) and exploded view with all components (right).

Fig. 2. Multi-layered PCB with Front View on Left Side and Bottom View on Right Side

been realized by using ABS printed molds with high accuracy. The external support for the connection with the gripper has been designed in order to be realized in aluminum by means of CNC machines.

A. Electronics Section

The electronic components of sensor are integrated on multi-layered PCBs, including optoelectronic based taxels and inertial measurement unit on a first main board with dimensions equal to 12.5×20 mm and Time of Flight sensor on a second board, connectable to first one, with dimensions equal to 12×8 mm. The main PCB is designed with new current driving channels for LEDs, optoelectronic section, buffering section and an efficient micro-controller with a sufficient number of Analog-to-Digital (A/D) channels for the tactile signals acquisition. The optoelectronic section consists of 8 taxels organized as shown in Fig. 2 with a spatial resolution equal to 3.55 mm. Each taxel exploits a photoreflector (manufactured by New Japan Radio, product code NJL5912R) composed of a LED and a photo-transistor, with the dimensions of $1.06 \times 1.46 \times 0.5$ mm. In previous version [16], each LED was powered with voltage supply but in the later version, LEDs are connected in series and they are driven by an adjustable current channel (manufactured by Texas Instrument, product code LM334) with an output current fixed to 4 mA. For the version proposed in this paper, by exploiting the high sensitivity of the optoelectronic component (NJL5912R), a new robust current source with output current equal to 1 mA is introduced in the circuit, in order to reduce also the power consumption of the sensor. The current channel implements the standard configuration available from datasheet, with single resistor, which yields the low temperature dependence characteristic, to fix the output current with high precision, from a voltage power supply. Analogue buffers have been introduced in the circuit, in order to decouple the voltage signals from photo-transistor and the A/D converter inputs: the low power operational amplifiers (Manufactured by Analog Devices, product code ADA4691) have been used in the voltage follower configuration. The low power micro-controller PIC16F19155 (Manufactured by Microchip), equipped with a 12-bit resolution on-board A/D converter, directly digitalized the buffer outputs. These low noise A/D converters enhance the signal to noise ratio and enables the simplification of firmware development. The IMU (Product code LSM6DSV16X, manufactured by STM Microelectronics) is another useful addition to the PCB. It provides 3-axis gyroscope, 3-axis accelerometer, 3-axis magnetometer and temperature, with also processing capabilities on board. It has multiple protocols of communication (i.e., Serial, I2C, SPI), but the developed sensor utilizes the I2C protocol.

Regarding the ToF sensor module, it was precisely designed to ensure self-consistency. All essential components required for seamless communication with the VL6180X device (manufactured by STMicroelectronics), and its power supply are incorporated on the module's PCB. Particularly, a Texas Instruments TPS76928 LDO Regulator is employed to provide the sensor with a stable 2.8 V power source. In addition, two NXP BSS138 components function as level shifters, adapting logic levels for the I2C bus. This compact module offers accessibility through a 6-way connector (Product code FTSH-

CAD Model of ToF Proximity PCB

Proximity Module

Integration of ToF PCB with Main PCB

Fig. 3. Time of Flight Sensor Module PCB

Fig. 4. Block Diagram of Electronic Components

103-04-F-DV, manufactured by Samtec) for communication with microcontroller. The details about the interconnection among ToF module and main board are reported in Fig. 9. Additional details about the ToF module can be found by the interested readers in [9]. The complete block diagram of all electronic components with connections is summarized in Fig. 4

B. Mechanical Parts

A fundamental part of this multi-modal sensor is the deformable pad, that can be realized in different shapes depending upon the application scenario. For example, as reported in [17], if information regarding torques and contact forces for manipulation are needed, a domed shaped deformable pad can be used for their reconstruction, by applying a trained neural network to tactile map signals. Alternatively, if object sizes are smaller with respect to pad and the objective is the recognition of object features for manipulation (e.g., the shape of a grasped wire), a pad with flat surface can be utilized [18].

Fig. 5. Rigid grid and deformable silicone Layer characteristics.

The design presented in this paper has flat surface, while the bottom side of the pad presents black walls, to optically isolate the taxels, and white cells in front of optical components, in order to maximize reflectivity, as reported in Fig. 5. The material used for the manufacturing of pad is silicone, due to its low hysteresis as well as good elastic property, compared to other deformable materials.

Between the deformable pad and main PCB, there is the rigid grid, which main objective is to ensure for the optoelectronic components to work within a monotonic range, since these components exhibit a non-monotonic behaviour when the reflective surface distance becomes less than $300\mu\text{m}$ [19]. In particular, the designed ensures that the distance of reflective surface from the photo-reflector cannot reach a value lower than $500\mu\text{m}$. The upper side of grid is designed in a way to connected with dark walls of pad, to enhance the interlinking robustness between deformable pad and rigid grid. The grid has been manufactured by 3D printing technology using black ABS plastic, with precision of about $\pm 100\mu\text{m}$ and the black color is selected to avoid undesired lateral reflections. The grid is bonded to deformable pad on one side and PCB on the other side (see Fig. 1), by means of a cyanoacrylate glue.

To complete the design of sensorized fingertip, a case for mounting and housing the multi-modal sensor has been designed. The case constitutes of two parts: a first part, manufactured by ABS plastic via 3D-printing technology, designed for isolating the bottom section of PCB from the mounting case; the second part which is the mounting case, realized in aluminium by means of CNC machining technique. The latter is composed of two sub-sections, that laterally slide to coincide at an intermediate point, and lock the deformable pad. These sub-parts got fixed with screws located at the back side of isolation shield, and the bottom sub-part has two holes for mounting the sensor on the commercial gripper's finger (see Fig. 1).

III. SOFTWARE DESIGN

This section describes the software developed for the interrogation of the sensors. It consists of two parts: the firmware on the microcontroller and the software for the external computer. The microcontroller is in charge of collecting data from the sensors and sending them via serial interface when requested by the connected PC.

A. Microcontroller Firmware

The firmware for microcontroller (MCU) has been developed with the idea to keep it as simple as possible to obtain a high acquisition rate for the sensor data. For this reason, all data processing and elaboration is delegated to other parts of the system, while the MCU, apart from initializing the sensors, is only responsible for acquiring data from the analog channels to which the photo-reflectors are connected, reading registers from the IMU and the ToF sensor through the I2C interface, and sending data on the serial interface. Pseudo-code reported in Algorithm 1 presents the developed firmware showing the operations carried out by the microcontroller.

Algorithm 1 Microcontroller Firmware

```
1: procedure MAIN
2:   Initialize System
3:   Configure ADC
4:   Configure I2C
5:   Configure Serial
6:   while true do
7:      $rxData \leftarrow \text{read } char$ 
8:     if  $rxData == a$  then
9:       for  $k \leftarrow 1$  to 8 do
10:         $tactData \leftarrow \text{data from analog channel } k$ 
11:        Send  $tactData$  over serial
12:      end for
13:     else if  $rxData == b$  then
14:       Send  $SensorID$ 
15:     else if  $rxData == c$  then
16:        $tofData \leftarrow \text{read ToF registers from I2C}$ 
17:       Send  $tofData$  over serial
18:     else if  $rxData == d$  then
19:        $imuData \leftarrow \text{read imu registers from I2C}$ 
20:       Send  $imuData$  over serial
21:     end if
22:   end while
23: end procedure
```

B. Elaboration Software (PC-Based)

Regarding the software for the elaboration of data, Robot Operating System (ROS) has been selected as the framework for handling the interprocess communication and task scheduling since it is broadly acknowledged within the robotics research community. Interrogation software, developed as a ROS node, is the one responsible for requesting data from the sensor and making it available for all the elaboration nodes on the ROS network. This software has been designed to

Fig. 6. Mechanical Integration within Three-Fingers Adaptive Gripper

offer maximum flexibility, regardless of the sensor types or the number of sensing elements. As for the data elaboration, instead, new ROS nodes can be easily added to the network since they only need to subscribe to the topics where sensor data is published.

IV. INTEGRATION AND TESTING

This section reports experimental results about the mechanical integration within robotic gripper and signal acquisition for the proposed sensing solution.

A. Integration with Three-Finger Adaptive Gripper

The multi-modal sensor designed for this study has been integrated on the three-finger adaptive gripper manufactured by Robotiq [20]. This integration engaged delicately aligning and installing the sensor on the gripper's structure to guarantee optimal performance and minimal interference with the gripper's functionality. Exceptional attention was given to the placement of the sensor to allow for effective data collection during gripping and manipulation tasks. The sensor was firmly attached to the gripper using custom-designed mounting brackets as shown in Fig. 6. This ensured stability and alignment, granting the sensor to gain data accurately during various gripping scenarios. The mechanical integration was executed to maintain the overall physical integrity of the gripper.

B. Testing Procedures

To evaluate the performance of the integrated multi-modal sensor, comprehensive testing experiments were conducted. The testing aimed to assess the sensor's capabilities in capturing tactile feedback, measuring time-of-flight proximity, and recording inertial measurements (i.e., accelerations, angular rates and temperature) during dynamic movements.

Fig. 7. Detection Peaks for Opto-electronic Components

1) *Tactile Signals*: The sensor was subjected to various objects with distinct surface textures, shapes, and materials. hence tactile capabilities were assessed by measuring the pressure distribution exerted on the gripper's fingers during gripping tasks with data acquisition at sampling frequency up to 1000 Hz. The corresponding data for tactile sensing are presented in Fig. 7, where raw voltages coming from the 8 taxels are reported. Data show how the raw signals present variations already sufficiently high and with low noise, to be easily used for robotic applications, without the needs of additional conditioning electronics and/or pre-processing algorithms.

2) *Time-of-Flight Proximity Signal*: The integrated proximity sensor can measure the distance from a target with a sampling frequency equal to 50 Hz. An example of distance measurements with a moving target is reported in Fig. 8, where the low-noise feature is clear. Then, the ToF proximity measurement was tested by analyzing its capability to detect the distance between the gripper and surrounding objects, positioned at different distances. In this case, a comparison of measured distances with ground truth data is reported in Fig. 9. The ToF measures have been computed as the mean value of 10 measurements, while for the ground truth, the distances have been acquired by means of a measuring scale. The experiments show a precision of the sensor almost equal

Fig. 8. Distance measurements from ToF sensor.

Fig. 9. Comparison of Time of Flight Measured and Reference distances.

Fig. 10. Accelerations Produced during Slippage

to its resolution, i.e., 1 mm. This results in higher percentage errors, i.e., $> 10\%$, when the object is very close to the sensor, and smaller errors, i.e., $< 1\%$, for farther objects.

3) *Inertial Measurement Unit Signals*: Dynamic movements of the gripper's fingers were analyzed using the integrated inertial measurement unit. The sensor's ability to gain accelerations, angular rates and temperature signals was evaluated during controlled motion sequences, providing data at a sampling frequency equal to 500 Hz. The data in Fig. 10 presents an example of accelerations measured during a closing, followed by an opening, of the gripper finger. The labels incorporated along the vertical axes, denoted as a_x , a_y , and a_z , serve to articulate the linear accelerations along the respective Cartesian axes, namely the x -axis, y -axis, and z -axis. From data, since a_y is almost zero, it is clear how the IMU have the y -axis orthogonal with respect to the plane in which the finger movement happens. Similarly, Fig. 11 reports the angular rates in degrees per second (dps) of the finger tip, measured by the IMU during an adduction-abduction movement, followed by a closing and an opening. In this case, the assigned labels denoting the angular rates as ω_x , ω_y , and ω_z around the x -axis, y -axis, and z -axis, respectively. Also in this case it is evident that during the adduction/abduction movement only a rotation around z -axis is visible (at about $t = 5$ s), while

Fig. 11. Angular Rate of the Finger-tip Measured by Gyroscope

Fig. 12. Temperature sensed by sensor equipped in IMU

during the closing/opening only a rotation around y -axis is visible (during the second part of experiment). Finally, the IMU allows also to obtain a measurement of temperature as reported in Fig. 12.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORKS

This work presented a new multi-modal sensing solution for robotic applications. In particular, the presented system integrates at the same time tactile sensors, ToF proximity sensors and IMU capable to measure accelerations, angular rates and temperature. The proposed design allow the integration in multi-fingered grippers or robotic hand by considering the reduced dimensions. The single measurement capabilities have been tested in order to evaluate sampling frequency, noise, precision. The system has been integrated into a commercial three fingered gripper and will be exploited in further works in order to implement control algorithms for robotic applications and/or data fusion algorithms for object features recognition.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work was partially supported by the European Commission under the Horizon Europe research grant IntelliMan (project no. 101070136) and by Università della Campania “Luigi Vanvitelli” under the TACMAN project.

REFERENCES

[1] A. Cirillo, M. Costanzo, G. Laudante, and S. Pirozzi, “Tactile sensors for parallel grippers: Design and characterization,” *Sensors*, vol. 21, no. 5, p. 1915, 2021.

[2] M.-S. Suen and R. Chen, “Capacitive tactile sensor with concentric-shape electrodes for three-axial force measurement,” *Proceedings*, vol. 2, no. 13. MDPI, 2018, p. 708.

[3] M. Makihata, M. Muroyama, S. Tanaka, T. Nakayama, Y. Nonomura, and M. Esashi, “Design and fabrication technology of low profile tactile sensor with digital interface for whole body robot skin,” *Sensors*, vol. 18, no. 7, p. 2374, 2018.

[4] Y. Wang, J. Chen, and D. Mei, “Flexible tactile sensor array for slippage and grooved surface recognition in sliding movement,” *Micromachines*, vol. 10, no. 9, p. 579, 2019.

[5] C. Liu, Y. Zhuang, A. Nasrollahi, L. Lu, M. F. Haider, and F.-K. Chang, “Static tactile sensing for a robotic electronic skin via an electromechanical impedance-based approach,” *Sensors*, vol. 20, no. 10, p. 2830, 2020.

[6] M. H. Rosle, Z. Wang, and S. Hirai, “Geometry optimisation of a hall-effect-based soft fingertip for estimating orientation of thin rectangular objects,” *Sensors*, vol. 19, no. 18, p. 4056, 2019.

[7] A. Mohammadi, Y. Xu, Y. Tan, P. Choong, and D. Oetomo, “Magnetic-based soft tactile sensors with deformable continuous force transfer medium for resolving contact locations in robotic grasping and manipulation,” *Sensors*, vol. 19, no. 22, p. 4925, 2019.

[8] J. Klimaszewski, D. Janczak, and P. Piorun, “Tactile robotic skin with pressure direction detection,” *Sensors*, vol. 19, no. 21, p. 4697, 2019.

[9] A. Cirillo, G. Laudante, and S. Pirozzi, “Proximity sensor for thin wire recognition and manipulation,” *Machines*, vol. 9, no. 9, p. 188, 2021.

[10] B. Mayton, L. LeGrand, and J. R. Smith, “An electric field pretouch system for grasping and co-manipulation,” in *2010 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation*. IEEE, 2010, pp. 831–838.

[11] L.-T. Jiang and J. R. Smith, “A unified framework for grasping and shape acquisition via pretouch sensing,” in *2013 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation*. IEEE, 2013, pp. 999–1005.

[12] A. Maldonado, H. Alvarez, and M. Beetz, “Improving robot manipulation through fingertip perception,” in *2012 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems*. IEEE, 2012, pp. 2947–2954.

[13] D. Guo, P. Lancaster, L.-T. Jiang, F. Sun, and J. R. Smith, “Transmissive optical pretouch sensing for robotic grasping,” in *2015 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS)*. IEEE, 2015, pp. 5891–5897.

[14] P. Lancaster, B. Yang, and J. R. Smith, “Improved object pose estimation via deep pre-touch sensing,” in *2017 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS)*. IEEE, 2017, pp. 2448–2455.

[15] K. Sasaki, K. Koyama, A. Ming, M. Shimojo, R. Plateaux, and J. Choley, “Robotic grasping using proximity sensors for detecting both target object and support surface. 2018 ieee,” in *RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS)*, 2018, pp. 2925–2932.

[16] G. De Maria, C. Natale, and S. Pirozzi, “Force/tactile sensor for robotic applications,” *Sensors and Actuators A: Physical*, vol. 175, pp. 60–72, 2012.

[17] M. Costanzo, G. De Maria, and C. Natale, “Two-fingered in-hand object handling based on force/tactile feedback,” *IEEE Transactions on Robotics*, vol. 36, no. 1, pp. 157–173, 2019.

[18] G. Palli and S. Pirozzi, “A tactile-based wire manipulation system for manufacturing applications,” *Robotics*, vol. 8, no. 2, 2019.

[19] M. Costanzo, G. De Maria, C. Natale, and S. Pirozzi, “Design and calibration of a force/tactile sensor for dexterous manipulation,” *Sensors*, vol. 19, no. 4, p. 966, 2019.

[20] Robotiq, “3-finger adaptive robot gripper,” 2020, accessed: 2024-06. [Online]. Available: <https://robotiq.com/products/3-finger-adaptive-robot-gripper>